

RESPONSE OF THREE MILLET VARIETIES TO NITROGEN FERTILIZER IN THE SEMI-ARID REGION OF NORTH-EAST NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Low soil fertility, especially N and P, are major constraints to increased food crop production and productivity in the sub-Saharan African (SSA). Field studies was undertaken to evaluate the response of millet cultivars (*Pennisetum* Spp) to different levels of nitrogen. The treatments consisted of factorial combinations of three cultivars (SOSAT-C88, LC-1C9702 and Ex-Borno) and four rates of nitrogen (0, 30, 60, 90 kg Nha⁻¹). Nitrogen levels as well as their interactions affected millet cultivars growth and yield. The cultivar LC-1C9702 out-performed SOSAT-C88 and Ex-Borno with respect to grain yield and harvested panicle per hectare at higher N level than the others. Ex-Borno could be sustained at the rate of 30 kg N/ha. Interaction between cultivars and fertilizer on stand count, plant height, panicle length, grain yield and harvested panicle were significant ($P < 0.05$).

KEYWORDS: Soil fertility, N fertilizer, millet yield, semi-arid.

INTRODUCTION:

Extensive research in West Africa has established that nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) are major limiting factors for sorghum and pearl millet production and this has lead to development of guidelines for improved production of these crops. N is the key nutrient for crop production. This element is the most mobile and also the most easily exhausted nutrients in the soil. Smallholder farmers rely on natural fallow periods and use of leguminous crops to restore soil N status (Nye and Greenland, 1960; Kwesiga and Coe, 1994; Hartemink *et al.* 1996). However, due to high population density and land pressure in sub humid tropics, long fallow periods are no longer sustainable. To sustain high crop yields in intensive and continuous crop production system, N fertilizer input is required. In this light, nitrogen supply from the soil needs to be assessed accurately in order to decide on the quantity of N fertilizer required to achieve the economic optimum yield and to avoid environmental contamination through excessive use (Goulding, 2000).

Millet is a common crop grown in the savanna ecologies. However, maize and sorghum are more dominant in the subhumid Guinea savanna than millet. Accordingly, Egharevba (1978) estimated that about five million hectares is sown to millet in Nigeria with an average yield of 350 kg ha⁻¹ in the Sahel. Millet crop was reported to perform better on marginal lands than other cereals (Tabo, 1995). The cultivars of millet released by the Lake Chad Research Institute, Maiduguri requires extensive information on its adaptability and agronomic practices among others. We decided to choose the three most promising cultivars of SOSAT-C88, LC-1C9702 and Ex-Borno. Though, Ex-Borno is a popular local check known for its compact head. This study was therefore, initiated to determine the effect of N fertilizer on the growth and yield of different millet cultivars.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was carried out in 2006 rainy season at the Lake Chad Research Institute Research and Demonstration Farm, Maiduguri in Borno State, Nigeria. Rainfall in the experimental site is mono-modal (500mm per annum) with a peak moisture regime in July and August which terminate in September/October. The soils are previously classified as Typic Ustipsamment (Nwaka and Kwari, 1993) with sandy loam in the top soils. The fields were ploughed and harrowed to a fine tilt and marked out into plots of 4.5 m x 5 m. Composite soil samples (0-20 cm) were taken for analyses of texture, pH, organic carbon, total N, available P, K, Ca, Mg, and Na (Van Reeuwijk, 1992).

The experiment was laid in a randomized complete block design replicated three times. Treatments consisted of three varieties, SOSAT-C88, LC-1C9702 and Ex-Borno; four levels of N fertilizer (0, 30, 60 and 90 kg N ha⁻¹).

Factorial arrangement of the three varieties and four levels of N-fertilizer constituted the 12 treatment combinations. Urea was the source of N fertilizer applied. Blanket application of 30 kg each of P₂O₅ and K₂O per hectare was done to ensure balanced plant nutrition. All the amount of P and K and half of N in accordance with the treatments were applied at sowing. The remaining half was applied by side dressing four weeks later. Seedlings were thinned to two plants/hill 7 to 10 days after emergence. Manual weeding was done at two and four weeks after sowing.

Stand establishment was determined by counting the total number of plants in a plot two weeks after sowing (WAS). The number of days to 50% flowering was determined by careful observation on daily basis when half the number of plants in a plot had flowered. Plant height was determined by randomly selecting ten plants per plot and measuring the heights from the ground level to the base of the panicle with a meter rule at full physiological maturity. Panicle length was determined by randomly selecting ten plant /plot and measuring the length from the base of the panicle to the tip with a meter rule at full physiological maturity. Panicle weight and grain yields were measured by recording the weight of panicles and threshed grains from each net plot using a Salter scale. These were then extrapolated to yield per hectare using the formula (Goldsworthy, 1964) Grain yield= Grain yield/net plot (kg) X 10,000m²/Net plot area (m²).

The data collected were subjected to analysis using GenStat (2003) Release 4.2 and differences between means were separated using the least significant difference (LSD 0.05).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data on the physico-chemical properties of soils is presented in Table 1. Sand fraction seems dominant with sandy loam texture. One striking feature of these soils is their low inherent fertility which, was expressed in low organic carbon (8 gkg⁻¹), total N (0.49 gkg⁻¹), available calcium (1.70) and magnesium (0.2) c mol (+) kg⁻¹ respectively. Though, the soil is very rich in phosphorus content, this might be traced to the historical management practices of the experimental site. In the near future, the soil may be faced with salinity/sodicity problem (Na= 0.70 C mol kg⁻¹). Deduced from the study, it is expected that only 1500kg ha⁻¹ of nitrogen would be produced. Of this, 750 kg (50%) represents the 'dynamic reserve'. Only about 1-4% of this is directly available for crop production (Smith, 2006) amounting to 7.5-30 kg ha⁻¹. Van Duivenbooden *et al.* (1996) estimated that for a target yield of 1000 kg ha⁻¹,

Table 1: Some physico-chemical soil properties of experimental site

Parameter	Value	Unit
Sand	74	%
Silt	18	%
Clay	8	%
pH H ₂ O	5.5	
Total Nitrogen	8	gkg ⁻¹
Organic carbon	0.49	gkg ⁻¹
Available phosphorus	34.90	mgkg ⁻¹
Exch. Potassium	0.19	C mol(+)kg ⁻¹
Exch. Sodium	0.70	C mol(+)kg ⁻¹
Exch. Calcium	1.70	C mol(+)kg ⁻¹
Exch. Magnesium	0.20	C mol(+)kg ⁻¹
Exch. Aluminium	0.10	C mol(+)kg ⁻¹
Classification	Typic Ustipsamment/ sandy loam	

millet removes 34.6, 5.0 and 48.8 kg ha⁻¹ N, P, and K from the soil compared with 30.7, 3.7 and 26.0 kg ha⁻¹ of N, P, and K removed by sorghum and 23.4, 3.5 and 16.6 kg ha⁻¹ of N, P, and K by maize. This indicates that millet is more likely to deplete soil nutrients at a faster rate than maize and sorghum.

Results on stand establishment, flowering and plant height presented in Table 2 indicated that, there was significant difference in stand establishment between the cultivars (p>0.05). This could be attributed to improved varieties and fertilizer applications. Cultivars EX-Borno proved adopted to the environment with highest stand count. Researchers (Kwari and Bibinu, 2002; Kumar, 1993) reported generally low stand establishment in Sudan and Sahel Savanna

Zones of Nigeria. Interaction effect of cultivar X fertilizer on stand establishment was significantly ($p < 0.01$). The combination of 60kgN/ha on EX-Borno depicts highest stand establishment in the experiment followed by LC-1C9702 and 0kgN/ha.

Table 2: Effect of nitrogen fertilizer on the growth and yield of millet varieties at Maiduguri

Variable	N	SC	HFL(DAS)	PHT(cm)	PL(cm)	GYD/ha(kg)	HP/ha(kg)
Overall	36	45	64.4	196.5	27.6	1689	2870
Cultivars		*	Ns	***	*	***	*
1(SOSAT-C88)		42	65.6	201.3	28.0	1713	2808
2(LC-1C9702)		45	63.4	190.5	27.9	1780	2954
3(EX-Borno)		47	64.3	197.6	26.8	1575	2848
LSD		4.18	1.9	4.5	1.6	102.0	142.6
Fertilizer		Ns	Ns	***	*	***	***
1(0kgN/ha)		41	64.3	185.3	26.9	1511	2411
2(30kgN/ha)		45	64.9	200.6	27.7	1422	2317
3(60kgN/ha)		48	64.3	197.8	27.4	1717	3069
4(90kgN/ha)		45	64.2	202.2	28.3	2107	3683
LSD		4.83	2.1	5.2	1.8	117.7	164.6
Cultivars x Fertilizer		**	Ns	***	*	***	***
1x1		36	64.7	181.7	27.0	1667	2567
1x2		44	67.0	216.7	28.7	1117	1900
1x3		40	66.0	199.3	29.3	1600	2733
1x4		47	64.7	207.7	27.0	2467	4033
2x1		49	63.3	183.0	26.3	1750	2800
2x2		43	64.0	195.3	29.0	1367	2383
2x3		45	63.0	196.3	28.0	1850	2933
2x4		42	63.3	187.3	28.3	2153	3700
3x1		37	65.0	191.3	27.3	1117	1867
3x2		48	63.7	189.7	25.3	1783	2667
3x3		58	64.0	197.7	25.0	1700	3542
3x4		47	64.7	211.7	29.7	1700	3317
LSD		8.36	3.7	9.0	3.2	203.9	285.1

N= Number of observations, SC= Stand count, HFL= Height of the flower length, PHT= Plant height, PL= Panicle length, GYD= Grain yield, HP= Harvested panicle. LSD= Least Significance Difference, *= Significant at ($< 0.05\%$), **= significant at ($< 0.01\%$), ***= Significant at (0.001%).

Flowering by the cultivars was not significantly influenced by nitrogen fertilization although, LC-1C9702 cultivar started flowering at 63 DAS. The earlier flowering in plots to which higher levels of nitrogen were applied might be partially due to enhanced availability of nutrient. Kowal and Knabe (1972) reported higher solar radiation prevalence in the Sahelian Savanna Zone against Sudan Savanna.

Plant height was significantly influenced by cultivars ($p < 0.001$). Cultivar SOSAT-C88 had the highest mean (201.33 cm) (Table 2). Plant height within levels of nitrogen fertilizer were greatest in 90kgN/ha > 30kgN/ha > 60kgN/ha > 0kgN/ha, respectively. Interaction effects of cultivar X fertilizer on plant height was significant ($P < 0.001$). The combined effect of SOSAT-C88 and 30kgN/ha gave the highest plant height. Though, did not translate to grain yield. Panicle length was significantly affected by the cultivars ($p < 0.05$) with cultivar SOSAT-C88 highest mean (28.00cm). The trend of individual levels of N was not statistically different. The combined effect of EX-Borno and 90kgN/ha gave the highest panicle length Table 2. Similar studies by Kwari and Bibinu (2002) confirms the assertion. This depicts that EX-Borno is more adapted to the Sahel and Sudan Savanna Zones than the Northern Guinea Savanna Zone.

The grain yield was significantly affected by cultivars ($P < 0.001$) Table 2. Cultivar (LC-1C9702) produced highest grain yield (1780 kg ha^{-1}) compared with the other two cultivars. The individual N levels were also significantly ($P < 0.001$) with 90 kg N/ha been highly responsive. There was lower response of 30 kg N/ha as against the control (0 kg ha^{-1}). The interaction between cultivars and fertilizer was also highly significant for grain yield of millet. Cultivar SOSAT-C88 was found to be responsive to nitrogen application and produced the highest grain yield (2467 kg ha^{-1}) at higher N level than the others. The responses of cultivars: SOSAT-C88 and LC-1C9702 to N rates followed the same pattern. At 30 kg N/ha the two cultivars shown no response when compared with 0 kg N/ha , 1117 and 1367 kg/ha , respectively. The high yielding cultivars can be promising in yield component when adequate nutrient is provided. In other words, high yielding cultivars are nutrient demanding. In balance nutrition is one among the factors of decline crop production and productivity in the tropics (Sanchez, 1976). Cultivar Ex-Borno is a popular local check and attained highest yield when 30 kg N/ha was applied. Application of 60 and 90 kg N/ha have statistically the same effect.

The harvested panicle kg/ha has its highest value in the cultivar LC-1C9702 (2954 kg/ha) as compared to SOSAT-C88 which was significantly ($P < 0.05$). The variation in grain yield between the cultivar could be attributed to many factors including the availability of nutrient in the soil and the gene responsible for the nutrient uptake. The interaction effect of cultivar and fertilizer on harvested panicle followed the same pattern as grain yield and were significantly ($P < 0.001$). The result suggests that production of millet in Maiduguri could be enhanced if SOSAT-C88 is combined with 90 kg N/ha . Similarly, cultivar (LC-1C9702) produced highest grain yield and harvested panicle 2153 and 3700 kg/ha with 90 kg N/ha . It is statistically different with other treatments (N rates). However, with lower rate of 30 kg N/ha , Ex-Borno produced highest grain yield (1783 kg/ha). Though, there was linear trend pattern in harvested panicle up till 60 kg/ha and diminished. This might be due to nutrient toxicity among others. Also cultivar (Ex-Borno) with 60 kg N/ha is promising. The saving of 30 kg N/ha could be substantial (see Table 2) as the yield difference between 2×4 and 3×3 is 158 kg/ha only.

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